

Cytotoxic properties of two families of benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone complexes of palladium

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Manuscript received online 16 July 2012, accepted 20 July 2012

Abstract : Reaction of 4-R-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (HL-R, where H stands for the dissociable hydrazinic proton and R (R = OCH₃, CH₃, H, Cl and NO₂) for the substituent) with *trans*-[Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] and Na₂[PdCl₄] afford complexes of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] and [Pd(L-R)₂] respectively. *In vitro* cytotoxicity screenings of these complexes along with four human clinical drugs, viz. cisplatin, BCNU, 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) and hydroxyurea, have been carried out in two human tumor cell lines, viz. promyelocytic leukemia HL-60 and histiocytic lymphoma U-937. Majority of these complexes show remarkably low IC₅₀ value and are found to be much more cytotoxic than the reference anticancer drugs in both the cell lines. Apoptosis study in HL-60 with two selected complexes from each group shows that at 5 and 10 μM concentration they induce apoptosis to a greater extent than cisplatin and camptothecin.

Keywords : Benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones, palladium complexes, cytotoxic properties.

Introduction

The chemistry of thiosemicarbazone complexes of the transition metal ions has been receiving significant current attention, primarily because of the bioinorganic relevance of these complexes¹. A large majority of the thiosemicarbazone complexes have found wide medicinal applications owing to their potentially beneficial biological (viz. antibacterial, antimalarial, antiviral and antitumor) activities². Systematic studies on the binding of thiosemicarbazones of selected types to different transition metal ions are of considerable importance in this respect. However, we have been exploring the chemistry of platinum metal complexes of the thiosemicarbazones³, mainly because of the variable binding mode displayed by these ligands in their complexes and also to understand the driving force behind the observed modes of binding. In a recent publication we have described the synthesis and characterization of two families of palladium complexes derived from five 4-R-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (HL-R, where H stands for the dissociable hydrazinic proton and R for the substituent), as well as their application as catalysts in C-C cross-

coupling reactions^{3m}. We have observed earlier that palladium complexes of thiosemicarbazone ligands exhibit remarkable cytotoxic properties towards different cancer cell lines³ⁱ, which have encouraged us to explore such properties in the palladium complexes of the selected 4-R-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones. It may be relevant to mention here that biological properties of palladium complexes of several thiosemicarbazone ligands have been studied well⁴. In the present study, which has emerged out of this exploration, we have selected two human cell lines, viz. promyelocytic HL-60 and lymphoma U-937, for assessing the cytotoxicity of the palladium complexes, and the observed results are reported herein.

Experimental

Materials :

Palladium chloride was obtained from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. The *trans*-[Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] and Na₂[PdCl₄] complexes were prepared by following reported procedures⁵. The benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (**1**) were prepared by reacting equimolar amounts of thiosemicarbazide and the respective *para*-substituted benzaldehyde in 1 : 1 ethanol-water mixture. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received. The [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] and [Pd(L-R)₂] (R = OCH₃, CH₃, H, Cl and NO₂) complexes were synthesized as reported earlier²⁴.

Cytotoxicity assay :

Cell lines and culture :

HL-60 and U-937 (purchased from National Center for Cell Sciences, Pune, India) were maintained in complete sterile growth medium RPMI-1640 with L-glutamine (GIBCO, Invitrogen Corporation, USA), containing 10% heat inactivated fetal bovine serum (GIBCO, Invitrogen Corporation, USA) and 1% antibiotics [10000 U penicillin/ml and 10000 µg streptomycin/ml, BioWhittaker, Cambrex Bio Science, USA]. Cell cultures were maintained in log phase using a subculture ratio of 1 : 5 twice a week.

Preparation of test material :

Working stock solutions of all the compounds were prepared by dissolving 20 mg of each compound in 1 ml of DMSO [Hybri-Max grade, Sigma-Aldrich Co., USA] and filtered under sterile condition. These were serially diluted with complete RPMI-1640 medium prior to use to obtain different drug concentrations.

MTT-based cytotoxicity test :

100 µl of cell suspension from the stock 2×10^5 HL-60 or 1×10^5 U-937 cells/ml were added to 96-well cell culture plates. Next 10 µl of drug solutions of different concentrations were added to respective wells followed by the addition of the medium (90 µl) in triplicate (total volume 200 µl/well). All vehicle controls contained the same concentration of DMSO. Plates were incubated for 72 h at 37 °C, 5% CO₂/95% air with humidity. After removal of 100 µl of media from each well, 10 µl of a 5 mg/ml solution of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-

diphenyltetrazolium bromide [MTT, Sigma, USA] in Dulbecco's PBS (GIBCO, BRL) were added to each well and the plate was incubated for 4 h at 37 °C. Subsequently 100 µl of acid isopropanol solution (0.04 N HCl in isopropanol) was added to the wells to dissolve formed formazan crystals. The plate was read in a microplate reader (Bio-Rad, USA, Model 550) at 540 nm. The percentage cell viability was calculated by dividing the average absorbance of the cells treated with compounds by that of the control; IC₅₀ (drug concentration needed for 50% inhibition of cells relative to control) was determined through Curvefit software by plotting % inhibition vs drug concentration and expressed in µM concentration.

In vitro apoptosis assay :

Induction of apoptosis *in vitro* by two representative complexes of each type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl], [Pd(L-R)₂], cisplatin and camptothecin were determined by a flow cytometric assay using an Annexin V-FITC⁶ Apoptosis Detection Kit (BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Diego, USA). Exponentially growing HL-60 cells in complete RPMI-1640 media (100 µl of 5×10^6) were plated in six well plates. 10 µl of each compound in DMSO (5 and 10 µM concentrations) was added to the wells followed by the addition of required media (total volume 1 ml). Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The cells were centrifuged at room temperature at 1500 rpm for 5 min. The pellet was washed twice with cold PBS and was re-suspended in the binding buffer (1X, 100 µl) provided in the Kit. The cells were stained with Annexin V-FITC (5 µl) and Propidium Iodide [PI] (5 µl) and incubated for 15 min in the dark at 25 °C. Next 400 µl of binding buffer was added to each tube and analyzed on a FACScan flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson, Mountainview, CA) using Cell Quest software. Two controls, viz. unstained cells and cells stained with both Annexin-V-FITC and PI, containing DMSO as vehicles were used. Cells that were annexin⁺/PI⁻ and annexin⁺/PI⁺ were considered positive for apoptosis.

Results and discussion

Syntheses and characterization :

As delineated in the introduction, five 4-R-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (**HL-R**) have been utilized in

the present study to synthesize new palladium complexes. When reactions of these selected thiosemicarbazones are carried out with *trans*-[Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂], taken as the source of palladium, in refluxing ethanol in the presence of triethylamine, a group of mixed-ligand complexes of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] are obtained in good yields. Thorough characterization on these complexes, including crystal

structure determination on two complexes, viz. [Pd(PPh₃)(L-CH₃)Cl] and [Pd(PPh₃)(L-NO₂)Cl], has shown that in these complexes the thiosemicarbazone ligands are coordinated to palladium as a bidentate N,S-donor forming a five-membered chelate ring. Comparison with the structure of uncoordinated thiosemicarbazone ligand has revealed that coordination of the benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone to palladium has taken place associated with an interesting, and rather uncommon, geometry change around the imine (C=N) bond.

To investigate whether bulk of the triphenylphosphine is responsible for the observed mode of binding of the benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (HL-R), their reaction has also been carried out with another palladium starting material, viz. Na₂[PdCl₄]. These reactions have afforded a second group of complexes of type [Pd(L-R)₂] in excellent yields. Crystal structures of two members of this family, viz. [Pd(L-OCH₃)₂] and [Pd(L-NO₂)₂], have been determined, which have again shown that in these bis-complexes also the thiosemicarbazone ligands are coordinated to palladium in the same fashion as before, which is associated with a change in geometry across the C=N bond.

Cytotoxicity study :

The *in vitro* growth inhibitory effect of the complexes

of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] and [Pd(L-R)₂] were evaluated on the two human cell lines viz. promyelocytic HL-60 and lymphoma U-937. Four human clinical drugs as cisplatin, BCNU, 5-FU and hydroxyurea were used as reference compounds for comparison. The activity is expressed in terms of IC₅₀, the concentration of the respective compound required to reduce the cell survival fraction to 50% after 72 h of exposure. The lower IC₅₀ values denote greater cytotoxicity. The results are presented in Table 1. In HL-60 cell line all the complexes of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] are around 6.5 fold more active than cisplatin and this type of activity is applicable to other

Table 1. Cytotoxic activities (IC₅₀, μM) of the complexes

Complex	Normal cell	HL-60	U-937
[Pd(PPh ₃)(L-OCH ₃)]	-	1.61	0.52
[Pd(PPh ₃)(L-CH ₃)]	-	1.53	2.11
[Pd(PPh ₃)(L-H)]	70.30	0.39	1.21
[Pd(PPh ₃)(L-Cl)]	-	1.54	1.66
[Pd(PPh ₃)(L-NO ₂)]	-	2.46	4.21
[Pd(L-OCH ₃) ₂]	-	0.206	0.208
[Pd(L-CH ₃) ₂]	115.51	0.098	0.041
[Pd(L-H) ₂]	-	0.175	0.056
[Pd(L-Cl) ₂]	-	0.375	0.056
[Pd(L-NO ₂) ₂]	-	1.27	19.91
Cisplatin	1804	7.0	3.2
BCNU	-	30.5	12.3
5-FU	-	266.0	4.7
Hydroxyurea	-	204.0	115.0

reference compounds. In this cell line all the complexes of the type [Pd(L-R)₂] are around 70 fold more active than cisplatin and also more active than other reference compounds. All the complexes of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)Cl] are more active than cisplatin and all other reference compound except [Pd(PPh₃)(L-NO₂)Cl] which is less than cisplatin and more than other reference compounds in U-937 cell line. All the complexes of type [Pd(L-R)₂] are around 25 fold more active than cisplatin and more active than other reference compounds in the above cell line. The complex [Pd(L-NO₂)₂] are more active than only hydroxyurea, less active than other reference compounds. Cytotoxicity assay has been done for one representative complex of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)] and [Pd(L-R)₂] in normal lymphocyte.

In vitro apoptosis assay :

The cell death may occur by one of two distinct mechanisms : necrosis or apoptosis. The most common and well-defined form of programmed cell death is apoptosis. During the past decade cell biology as well as oncology research has focused on apoptosis. The type of cell death induced by the complexes was investigated by Annexin V-FITC/PI apoptosis assay in a flow cytometer. The assay was restricted to two representative complexes from each group having lower IC₅₀ values in HL-60. The results obtained for the complexes at 24 h of incubation time in HL-60 have been compared with those for cisplatin and camptothecin, an apoptosis inducer, which are shown in Fig. 1. Each treatment with drug was carried out at 5 and 10 μM concentration. Exposure of cells to cisplatin resulted in a 1.39% and 1.20% induction of gated cell in

Fig. 1. (contd.)

Fig. 1. Flow cytometric analysis of apoptosis and necrosis in HL-60 cells after treatment with four drugs or complexes at two different concentration. Quadrant analysis of fluorescence intensity of gated cells in FL-1 and FL-2 channels was from 10000 events. Figures in the cytogram indicate the percent of gated cells in each quadrant. (FL1-H = Annexin-V, FL2-H = Propidium iodide).

LR⁷ Annexin V⁺/PI⁻ cells (lower right quadrant, representing early apoptotic cells) and, 3.23% and 6.31% cell in UR respectively (Fig. 1C and 1D). Camptothecin induces 7.79% and 10.52% cells in LR and 5.46% and 5.30% cells in UR (Fig. 1E and 1F). In the [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)] and [Pd(L-R)₂] group of complexes, first apoptotic study has been done for [Pd(PPh₃)(L-H)] and [Pd(L-Me)₂] complex which having least IC₅₀ value. To verify whether lower IC₅₀ correspond to better apoptosis, apoptosis study of [Pd(PPh₃)(L-OCH₃)] and [Pd(L-H)₂] complex have been done having next lower IC₅₀ value. The [Pd(PPh₃)(L-OCH₃)] complex induces 1.47% and 1.06% cells in LR and 32.16% and 62.70% cells in UR (Fig. 1G and 1H).

The [Pd(PPh₃)(L-H)] complex induces 3.14% and 2.87% cells in LR and 42.80% and 63.85% cells in UR (Fig. 1I and 1J). In case of [Pd(L-R)₂] group of complexes apoptosis study of [Pd(L-Me)₂] complex has been done which having least IC₅₀ value. This complex induces 0.59% and 1.16% cells in LR and 95.10% and 77.52% cells in UR (Fig. 1K and 1L). [Pd(L-H)₂] complex induces 0.85% and 1.51% cells in LR and 85.57% and 63.11% cells in UR (Fig. 1M and 1N). All the complexes show better apoptosis than cisplatin and camptothecin.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that the two families of benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone complexes of palladium of type [Pd(PPh₃)(L-R)] and [Pd(L-R)₂], in which the thiosemicarbazone ligands display a rather uncommon coordination mode involving a restricted rotation around the imine bond, have remarkable cytotoxicity towards the HL-60 and U-937 cell lines, which, in some cases, is even better than that of recognized anticancer drugs, as manifested in the IC₅₀ values and further corroborated by the apoptosis study.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance received from the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi [Grant No. 01(2384)/10/EMR-II] is gratefully acknowledged. Piyali Paul thanks the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for her fellowship [Grant No. 09/096(0588)/2009-EMR-I].

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7. Abbreviations used : LR (Lower Right quadrant, represent-

ing early apoptotic cells which are Annexin V⁺/PI⁻); UR (Upper Right quadrant, representing late apoptotic cells which are Annexin V⁺/PI⁺).